

“TEACHER’S LANGUAGE:HOW CLASSROOM LANGUAGE AFFECTS STUDENT’S
MOTIVATION AND CONFIDENCE”

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Abstract. *This research explores the topic “Teacher’s Language:How classroom language affects student’s motivation and confidence”.The study investigates how the language used by teachers during lessons-including tone,word choice,feedback style,and the use of motivational or discouraging phrases-impacts students`self-confidence and enthusazim for learning.Special attention is given to the psychological and emotional effects of both positive and negative language on learners.The findings highlight the crucial role of teacher communication in creating a supportive and engaging learning environment.By examining real-life classroom interactions,this research emphasizes the importance of developing teacher language awareness as a tool to foster student motivation and build a confident classroom culture.*

Keywords: *Teacher`s classroom language,motivational language strategies,confidence-building in students,verbal and non-verbal communication,student-teacher interaction,impact of teacher speech on learners,pedagogical discource,emotional influence of language,supportive learning environment,educational communication techniques,positive reinforcement,classroom management through language,affective factors in education,linguistic aspects of teaching,teacher feedback language.*

In today`s educational landscape,the role of the teacher extends far beyond delivering academic content;it encompasses shaping students`attitudes,self-perceptions,and emotional responses to learning.One of the most powerful tools a teacher possesses is language-the very words they choose,the tone they use,and the messages they convey in classroom settings.Teacher language not only serves as a medium of instruction but also acts as a psychological and emotional force that can significantly affect students` motivation and confidence.The classroom is a social environment where interactions,especially verbal ones,have lasting affects on learners` development.Motivation and self-confidence are two crucial elements in a student`s educational success.Motivation drives the desire to learn,persist through challenges,and strive for improvement,while self-confidence allows students to trust their abilities and take risks in the learning process.Numerous studies in educational psychology and pedagogy suggest that both motivation and confidence are strongly influenced by the classroom environment-particularly by the nature of teacher-student communication.A supportive,encouraging techer can inspire students to reach their full potential,whereas a critical or disengaged teacher may unintentionally diminish a student`s enthusazim and belief in their abilities.In language classrooms or any general learning environment,the daily interactions between teacher and student create a learning climate.Teachers who use inclusive ,motivating,and a emphatic language can foster a positive classroom culture where students feel safe,respected,and encouraged to participate.On the contrary,language that is overly harsh,dismissive,or lacking in positive reinforcement may lead to disengagement,anxiety,or even academic withdrawl.Words such as “good job”, “keep trying”,or “I believe in you” may seem simple,but they carry immense power in shaping students` self-worth and academic

identity. Furthermore, the consistency of such language use and the emotional tone it carries are equally vital.

This study focuses on the relationship between teacher language and its impact on students' motivation and confidence during classroom interactions. It aims to identify which specific verbal strategies contribute positively or negatively to the learners' psychological and academic outcomes. By examining both encouraging and discouraging language patterns, the research intends to highlight how subtle differences in teacher speech can have significant consequences. The importance of this topic lies not only in improving teaching practices but also in addressing broader concerns about student well-being, equity, and engagement in education. In a time when student mental health and motivation are widely discussed, understanding the role of teacher communication becomes essential. Thus, this study seeks to raise awareness among educators about the influence of their words and promote reflective language use that supports student growth and resilience.

Several researchers have explored the role of teacher language in influencing students' learning experiences, motivation, and emotional well-being. One of the foundational theories relevant to this topic is Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), which emphasizes the importance of language in shaping thought and learning through interaction. According to Vygotsky, a teacher's language provides cognitive support and creates a social environment where learners feel encouraged to participate and take risks. Dornyei (2001) further highlights that motivation in the classroom is strongly connected to teacher behavior especially language use. He argues that supportive, encouraging comments help increase students' engagement, while negative or indifferent language can reduce learners' desire to participate. Simple phrases like "Well done", "That's a great idea" can go a long way in building confidence. In more recent studies, Mercer and Dawes (2014) examined how dialogic teaching-language that invites students into meaningful discussion-can increase classroom participation and self-confidence. When teachers ask open-ended questions and listen actively, students feel that their ideas matter.

After exploring how teacher language affects students' motivation and confidence in classroom settings, I have come to several conclusions based on both the reviewed literature and my own educational experiences. As a student and future educator, I deeply believe that the words a teacher chooses are not just sounds-they carry emotional, cognitive, and even lifelong weight. There are some personal recommendations and overview ideas:

1. Promote positive and encouraging language use:

Teachers should consistently use affirming and constructive language to motivate learners.

2. Implement student-centered communication techniques:

Educators are encouraged to adopt more interactive and student-friendly communication style.

3. Integrate classroom language training into teacher education:

Understanding how language affects motivation, anxiety, and self-esteem can lead to more mindful and impactful teaching.

I would recommend that teachers become more consciously aware of their daily language use. Many teachers may not realize how even small comments-both positive and negative-can shape a student's attitude toward learning. Encouraging phrases such as "you are improving", "Keep

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going”, “I am proud of you” can make a tremendous difference, especially for students who are shy or struggling. I believe that teachers should always try to see the learner behind the mistake. Every student brings emotions, fears, and hopes into the classroom. When teachers speak with kindness, they speak not only to the mind, but also to the heart. That's the real power of language education. Additionally, students should be made aware of the importance of respectful communication. Teacher-student interaction is a two-way street. When both sides use constructive, polite, and kind language, the space becomes a growing space. The findings of this study highlight the significant role that teachers' language plays in shaping students' motivation, confidence, and overall learning experience. It was observed that the way teachers speak to students—whether consciously or unconsciously—can leave a lasting impact on how learners perceive themselves and their academic potential. The emotional climate created by classroom language also influences long-term academic performance and attitude toward learning. Language that fosters inclusion, empathy, and positive reinforcement is key to maintaining a supportive learning environment, especially for students who may be struggling or lack belief. The study supports the view that warm, respectful, and student-centered communication builds trust and increases learners' willingness to participate. When students feel heard, valued, and respected by their teachers, they are more likely to engage with course material, ask questions, and take academic risks without the fear of being judged or criticized. Conversely, the use of harsh or excessively authoritative language was shown to decrease classroom interaction and lower students' self-confidence.

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